

Spatial density maps from a debris cloud

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Introduction

Outline

- 1 Introduction
- 2 Exact density map calculation
- 3 Study
- 4 Results
- 5 Discussion

Concentrations of debris and their duration

- We want to know about the distribution of debris after a fragmentation.
- Accustomed to thinking of terrestrial debris, many think of space debris as forming a *debris field*.
- Are there concentrations of density?
- Do the concentrations persist in some/most/all locations?
- What of the concentrated areas are due to the initial velocity distribution, and what are due to dynamics?

Understand the structure and evolution with an exact calculation of spatial density

- In order gain this understanding and answer these questions, we have developed a new approach.
- View: inertial space with a density of objects, instead of objects with ephemeris in inertial space.
- In the language of fluid dynamics, shift from *Lagrangian* view to *Eulerian* view.
- No relative motion approximation, no Gaussian distribution assumption, or any other approximation.
- No sampling or Monte Carlo simulation.

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Exact computation for any time

- We want an exact calculation of the *density* of objects at any point at any time, for any input density of velocities at the fragmentation point.
- Full three dimensional input and output.
- *Transformation of variables* tells you how a density G_X transforms under a function $F : X \rightarrow Y$ to G_Y .
- The density at a point is the sum over the densities at the inverse images F^{-1} divided by the absolute value of the forward Jacobian determinant at those points

$$G_Y(y) = \sum_{x \in F^{-1}(y)} \frac{G_X(x)}{|\det J_F(x)|}.$$

- Jacobian is the matrix of partial derivatives.

Solving the map and Jacobian determinant

- Solve the Lambert problem between the fragmentation point \vec{r}_1 and the point (pixel) of interest \vec{r}_2
- Battin's hypergeometric method solves a variable $x > -1$; from that the full initial velocity $\dot{\vec{r}}_1$ can be found
- Partial derivatives $\partial\vec{r}_2/\partial\dot{\vec{r}}_1$ worked out by Battin and untangled by Arora et al. (2015) as a straightforward algebraic calculation.
- Jacobian determinant has units of cubic time, values around $10^{10}s^3$.
- Dividing into a density in velocity space yields a density in position space.

Getting all the solutions

- It is important for the density transformation computation that *all* inverse images and therefore Lambert solutions be found.
- Lambert modes
 - Number of whole orbits: $N = 0$, $N > 0$ solutions, up to the maximum possible for the given elapsed time ($N > 0$ has a minimum time)
 - Short way, long way.
 - For $N > 0$, there are two solutions if elapsed time is greater than the minimum time.
- There are $2(N_{\max} + 1)$ *mathematical solutions* possible, where N_{\max} is the largest value of N whose minimum time is less than or equal to the elapsed time.
- Include unbound orbits (parabolic, hyperbolic; $N = 0$), if there will be enough velocity.
- *Physical solutions* are those mathematical solutions whose trajectory does not intersect the earth.

Density map

- For each elapsed time and each point on a grid, compute all inverse images, velocity \vec{r}_1 and $|\det J_F|$.
- Look up initial velocity distribution.
- Divide velocity density by $|\det J_F|$ and sum over inverse images, that gives density for that $\vec{r}_2(t)$.
- Do all points in a grid, render as image.

Volume and persistence of dense areas

- Count volume above a threshold of density at each time step.
- Count fraction of that volume above the threshold that was above the threshold on the previous step (persistence).
- Plot at various thresholds that represent levels of concern over time.

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Simulated fragmentation

- Satellite in a 900 km altitude circular orbit.
- Instantaneous fragmentation with one of two velocity distributions.
 - 1 “Top hat” constant, isotropic distribution up to a maximum of Δv of 2kms^{-1} . Maximum speed is 9.4kms^{-1} , maximum apogee is just over 30Mm.

- 2 NASA EVOLVE 4.0, exponential in the log of Δv , for $A/m=0.1\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$, no maximum Δv , isotropic.

Location and duration of computation

- Density is computed in the original orbital plane.
- Full HD video, 1920x1080, shown here reduced.
- 24 km spacing between pixels.
- Earth is along the right-hand edge.
- First 8 hours after fragmentation: 15 minutes = 1 second.
- Then to 36 hours after fragmentation, 1 hour = 1 second.
- Green dot showing one orbit pre-fragmentation, then ghost satellite orbit after fragmentation.
- Density shown on a zero-logarithmic color scale, partially logarithmic (represent zero by fading to black, above threshold in white).

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Top hat movie

Top hat at 40m

Top hat at one hour

Top hat at 1h20m

Top hat at 1h50m

Top hat at 2h40m

Top hat at 3h40m

Top hat at 4h30m

Top hat at 6 hours

Top hat at 8 hours

Top hat at 12 hours

Top hat at 24 hours

Top hat at 36 hours

Initial behavior

- Initially, high density ball, as it orbits, spreads out and becomes less dense.
- First visible inhomogeneity in the density is antipodal, at the anti-pinch line.
- Soon, forms into a banana shape (including the stem!).
- Curves back toward pinch point, forming the first band.
- Meanwhile, the outer tail of the lowest density region is moving outward and getting less dense.
- Start to see the superposition of bands
- Notice band has an outer edge of high density immediately adjacent to the no-solution region (gap).

Anti-pinch line

- The anti-pinch line is distinctly noticeable after about an hour.
- It is caused by the appearance of two $N = 0$ (zero orbit) solutions.
- Because the earth blocks long-way solutions that are too close to the original point, the double solution is only possible near the antipodal line.
- As the first (outer) band moves out of the field of view at about three hours, it takes with it most of that concentrated density.

After 8 hours

- Front of density “band factory” wave cycles around at original orbit radius, creating new bands.
- As new bands are created and move outward, they overlap the old bands.
- The boundaries of the bands are clearly visible in this case as superposition of the individual densities.
- Between the bands, the zero-density gaps on the antipodal side start out very broad, and gradually fill in.
- At around 18 hours, the bands in the middle are just starting to completely overlap.
- The “fronts” of the bands have a sudden drop off in density with increasing radial distance, from the very highest density to actually or almost nothing, while the climb back up in density is much more gradual.

EVOLVE movie

EVOLVE at 40m

EVOLVE at one hour

EVOLVE at 1h20m

EVOLVE at 1h50m

EVOLVE at 2h40m

EVOLVE at 3h40m

EVOLVE at 4h30m

EVOLVE at six hours

EVOLVE at eight hours

EVOLVE at 12 hours

EVOLVE at 24 hours

EVOLVE at 36 hours

Areas of concentrated risk

- Areas with high density exceeding a threshold (say 10^{-11}km^{-3}) are the only ones of concern.
- Find the total volume that exceeds this threshold.
- Look at its dependence in time.
- Find stable concentration: fraction of the volume exceeding the threshold for which it exceeded on the previous time step.

Volume of concentrated areas top hat

Volume of concentrated areas EVOLVE

Persistent concentrated areas top hat

Persistent concentrated areas EVOLVE

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Exact, calibrated, density

- It is possible to do an exact calculation of spatial density using the transformation of variables method.
- Simulations from 900km circular orbit.
- Flat bounded “top hat” Δv fragmentation distribution.
- NASA EVOLVE 4.0 for $A/m=0.1\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$, unbounded.
- There are similar structures: pinch point, anti pinch line, bands, etc., so are common to the dynamics rather than the initial velocity distribution.
- Anti-pinch line is more commonly broken line segments.
- Bands move out and densities superpose; the boundaries are clearly visible.
- Eventually, gaps between the bands fill in.
- These are likely due to the dynamics.

Differences between the velocity distributions

- EVOLVE relative concentration of density nearer the earth, rather than spread out far from the earth.
- Lack of sharp cutoff in distance from the earth.
- Characteristics of the initial Gaussian-logarithm distribution, with peak around 45 m/s.
- Faster filling of bands.
- Further spread of debris.

Concentrations of density and their persistence

- Concentrated areas in the original orbital plane, which are of greatest concern for spacecraft operations
- After initial transients and oscillations lasting a few hours, the total volume of concentrated areas settles to a nearly constant level.
- Exception: EVOLVE at the lowest threshold 10^{-11}km^{-3} (may settle after 36 hours).
- In both models virtually all of the concentrated areas are static (after initial transients), indicating they are phenomena of the dynamics rather than the initial velocity distribution.
- Note that stasis of concentrated area does *not* mean that a particle stays there, they are all still subject to orbital motion, so the “debris field” concept doesn’t apply in that sense.

Conclusion

- Within 20 or so orbits of fragmentation, spatial density evolution is quite complicated.
- Pinch point, anti-pinch broken line that fills in, bands, fronts, etc.
- Bands spread and merge together.
- Areas of highest concentration (10^{-11}km^{-3} and above) are almost all stable after a few hours.
- EVOLVE vs. top hat: more concentration on inner orbits, no upper limit on outer reaches, initial concentrated antipodal line after half an orbit moves outward and fades, to be replaced by broken line.